

1 **Improved accuracy of environmentally relevant parameter estimates derived from**
2 **biodegradation assays**

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11 **Highlights**

12 Accuracy of (enantio)biodegradation/analytical processes is improved

13 Environmental information is based on analytical signals and biodegradability

14 A novel Monod based biodegradability model is proposed

15 **ABSTRACT**

16 Biodegradation assays involve both biodegradation and analytical processes which can
17 be affected by systematic errors, among others. These errors can affect all the
18 environmentally relevant parameters related to biodegradability, enantioselectivity (in
19 the case of chiral compounds), kinetic parameters and persistence of chemicals.
20 However, such impacts have never been well-characterized. In this work, calculations
21 and models used for a long time are studied by simulating systematic errors at the 5 %
22 level, which affect independently the analytical calibration step and the biodegradation
23 process. The impact of these errors is also compared with those obtained from an
24 alternative approach: recently proposed equations and a novel model (a Monod

25 modified version) developed in this work. All simulations are compatible with an
26 environmentally relevant pollutant concentration. The results suggest a high degree of
27 minimization (or even cancelation) of the systematic error impact using the alternative
28 approach respect to the conventional one. These findings can be interpreted either in
29 view of achiral or chiral pollutants. The present work can have a positive impact in the
30 area of risk assessment of new pollutants and hazardous materials.

31 ***Capsule:***

32 The global accuracy of estimates of environmentally relevant parameters (rate constant,
33 half-life time and enantiomeric fraction for chiral compounds) is remarkably improved
34 using a new simple approach based on a novel Monod-based model.

35 ***Keywords:***

36 Biodegradability; Kinetics; Half-life time; Enantioselectivity; Accuracy; Analytical
37 signal

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44 **1. Introduction**

45 Pollutants can reach the environment as a consequence of a wide variety of
46 human activities (Liao et al., 2018). The persistence of these compounds in the
47 environment is related with their potential to undergo biodegradation processes (Pizzo
48 et al., 2016). A pollutant biodegradation assay, which includes an analytical step,
49 produces analytical signals (e.g. chromatographic peak areas (Escuder-Gilabert et al.,
50 2018a)) that can be used for estimating several environmentally relevant parameters:
51 biodegradability (*BD*), indicating the biodegradation degree of the pollutant; kinetic
52 parameters from a given kinetic model; as well as parameters linked to its persistence in
53 the environment, such as the half-life time (*HL*) (Escuder-Gilabert et al., 2018b; ECHA,
54 2017; Pizzo et al., 2016). In addition, in the case of a chiral pollutant, the enantiomeric
55 fraction (*EF*) can also be estimated (Escuder-Gilabert et al., 2018a; Escuder-Gilabert et
56 al., 2018b).

57 The closer the bioassay conditions to the environmental ones the higher the
58 relevance of the results, despite the higher cost and difficulties (McLachlan et al., 2017).
59 This fact has promoted the use of OECD tests at three tiered levels: ready (first level)
60 and inherent (second level) biodegradability tests, and simulation tests (third level). The
61 third level has higher complexity and approaches the processes at environmental
62 compartments or treatment plants (ECHA, 2017).

63 Environmentally relevant parameter can be estimated using some conventional
64 equations and kinetic models. Table 1a summarises a conventional approach to estimate
65 all the parameters from a single biodegradation assay. This approach uses the Monod
66 model, which is applicable regardless of the microbial growth-linked biodegradation of
67 the pollutant or its concentration (*S*) during the assay; i.e. from ppm- (as in ready
68 biodegradability tests) to ppb-level or lower (as in field assays) (Robinson and Tiedje,

69 1983; Liu and Zachara, 2001; Boethling et al., 2009). First-order kinetics (a popular
70 model), is in fact a particular case of the Monod model. It is normally used without
71 verifying their intrinsic assumptions related to concentration or the biomass growth (a
72 difficult task) (Robinson and Tiedje, 1983; Liu and Zachara, 2001; Boethling et al.,
73 2009). In the case of the Monod model, the ratio between the Monod parameters, r , is
74 proportional to the first-order constant. The “biological half-life” concept refers to the
75 time required for the amount of a substance in a biological system to be reduced to one
76 half of its value by biological processes, when the rate of removal is approximately
77 exponential (e.g. first-order decay) (IUPAC, 2019). Since first-order model adequacy
78 could be difficult to assure, *HL* has been approached as the time value corresponding to
79 $BD = 50\%$ (Escuder-Gilabert et al., 2018a; Escuder-Gilabert et al., 2018b).

80 On the other hand, the quality of the estimated parameters depends not only on
81 errors affecting time-dependent biodegradation process, but also on the analytical
82 process (e.g. the calibration step to transform analytical signals into concentrations).
83 Errors of both processes are independent. For instance, in the calibration stage,
84 interfering or matrix effects are well-known sources of systematic errors. Examples of
85 inaccuracy in the biodegradation process stage can be found in (Escuder-Gilabert et al.,
86 2018b). Unfortunately, there are very few studies dealing with the impact of errors on
87 the estimates, and they are focused only on random errors in the bioprocess (not the
88 calibration stage) and on kinetic parameter estimations (not on other parameters)
89 (Robinson and Tiedje, 1983; Liu and Zachara, 2001). The impact of systematic errors
90 on environmentally relevant parameters like *BD*, *EF* (for chiral pollutants), or *HL* has
91 not been reported. To the best of our knowledge this is the first report on this issue, but
92 also on the proposal of an alternative approach to improve its accuracy; an intrinsic goal
93 of analytical chemists.

94 In this work, the accuracy of parameters related to the conventional approach in
95 Table 1a (calculations and models; used for long time), is characterized by simulating
96 systematic errors at the 5 % level, affecting independently the analytical calibration
97 stage and the analytical signal from a biodegradation/analytical processes. The impact
98 of these errors is compared with those obtained by a proposed alternative approach. It
99 includes recently proposed equations, based on the direct use of the analytical signal (A)
100 instead of the concentration data (Escuder-Gilabert et al., 2018a). These equations were
101 aimed at eliminating the calibration uncertainty contribution, but they were not been
102 tested in terms of accuracy. The alternative approach also includes a novel model
103 introduced in this work (adapted from the conventional Monod equation). All
104 simulations are compatible with an environmentally relevant pollutant concentration.
105 The aim is to evaluate the possibilities of reducing or eliminating the impacts of the
106 inevitable systematic errors on parameter estimations by using the alternative approach.
107 Since this work is focused on accuracy, the study can only be approached by
108 simulations, due the lack of references from real biodegradation processes. For
109 simplicity, the simulations assume a chiral compound but a non-enantioselective
110 biodegradation process. The results can be interpreted in an achiral or in a chiral way.

111

112 **2. Material and methods**

113 Tables 1a and 1b show the variables and equations used in this work for the
114 conventional and alternative approaches, respectively. The last one includes a new
115 version of the integrated Monod equation (Eq. (4a)), proposed in this work, and
116 obtained by substituting the concentration (S) by biodegradability (BD) according to Eq.
117 (2). The two approaches are compatible with an enantioselective biodegradation study,
118 being the corresponding enantiomers the final analytes to be determined. True values

119 for the estimates (S , A , BD , EF , r and HL) are obtained from the model and equations of
120 Table 1a. Since they are error-free values they are used as reference data to establish the
121 accuracy degree of the approaches (expressed as relative errors in percentage).
122 Experimental-like results for the estimates are obtained using both approaches (for
123 comparison purposes), after provoking systematic errors either in the calibration step
124 (regression coefficients: intercept, b_0 , or slope, b_1) or the analytical signal (A), are then
125 compared with those reference values. A particular case has been evaluated here
126 (simulation conditions, provoked systematic errors, degree of enantioselectivity of the
127 biodegradation stage, incubation times, etc.). Different conditions alter the magnitude of
128 the errors in some cases (not shown), but not the conclusions respect the comparison
129 between approaches.

130 Simulation conditions, using dimensionless true parameters, as suggested in Liu
131 and Zachara, include as fixed parameters: $S_0 = 0.001$ as initial pollutant concentration.
132 $\mu_m = 0.5$ and $K_s = 20$ as true Monod kinetic parameters for both enantiomers, then a non
133 enantioselective biodegradation process is simulated (i.e. $EF = 0.5$ as the true value).
134 Monod variables are also fixed: $X_0 = 0.2$ and $Y = 0.2$. The true r ($\mu_m/K_s = 0.025$) is
135 proportional to the corresponding first-order rate constant (Liu and Zachara; 2001). For
136 simplicity, three incubation times, t (0, 7 and 14), are used. Simulations of
137 experimental-like results using more times (not shown) provide equal conclusions, so
138 they become unnecessary. However, in view of a precise HL estimation by
139 interpolation, t is increased from 0 to 40 in 0.01 increments (short t-increments) for the
140 steps 6 and 6a in Tables 1a and 1b, respectively. The calculations and models in Tables
141 1a and 1b generate three estimations for the output variables A , S , BD and EF and a
142 single output for r and HL .

143 True calibration parameters are $b_0 = 0$ and $b_1 = 1$; thus, true A and S values
144 coincide. In this work, systematic errors have been provoked either in b_0 or b_1
145 (simulating errors in the method calibration stage) or in A (simulating an error in the
146 analytical signals measurement during the biodegradation process). In both cases, they
147 have been provoked for just one (E1) or both enantiomers (E1 and E2 simultaneously).
148 In all cases, these provoked errors are set at the 5 % level (relatively moderate), as
149 indicated in Tables 2a and 2b.

150

151 **3. Results and discussion**

152 Tables 2a and 2b show the results obtained from the accuracy simulation study
153 affecting the calibration and signal, respectively. For clarity, they only show the
154 erroneous results obtained from the equations and steps in Tables 1a and 1b. In other
155 words, accurate equations, providing null or negligible errors (due to modeling causes),
156 are not included in these tables. The analysis of all the results provide a comparison of
157 the strategies from a chiral point of view. To achieve an achiral point of view, the
158 results of E1 (odd rows in Table 2a and 2b); except for EF outputs) should be
159 assimilated to those of an achiral compound (with the same concentration as E1; $S_0/2$).

160 Table 2a results correspond to provoked errors in the calibration stage
161 (regression coefficients), involving only one enantiomer (E1) or both simultaneously
162 (E1, E2). As can be seen in Table 1b, the alternative approach has no the steps 1 and 2
163 of the conventional one, avoiding the calibration step as suggested in (Escuder-Gilabert
164 et al., 2018a). This is then a first advantage of this approach from an experimental point
165 of view. Consequently, experimental errors on the intercept (b_0) or slope (b_1) does not
166 affect this strategy (i.e. equations from Table 1b do not appear in Table 2a), but affect

167 all the estimates calculated using the conventional one; Table 1a; i.e. all Eqs. (2), (3),
168 (4) and step 7 appear in Table 2a.

169 The calibration errors affect the conventional approach at different degrees,
170 depending on the parameters (Table 2a). Resultant errors in the biodegradability
171 estimate by Eq. (2) are of the same level ($\sim 5\%$) than the error provoked in the intercept
172 (b_0). However, an error provoked in the slope (b_1) provides no error in BD from Eq. (2)
173 when only E1 is involved or -2.4% errors when E1 and E2 are involved. Estimates of
174 the enantiomeric fraction derived from Eq. (3) are erroneous only when the provoked
175 errors affect one enantiomer. This fact leads to a false positive indication of
176 enantioselectivity (i.e. EF varying from the true 0.5 value). If the error is provoked in
177 the slope, the resultant error in EF is -2.4% regardless of t . In contrast, errors in the
178 intercept provide EF errors that increase with time, giving the false appearance of a
179 progressive enantioselective biodegradation process. The errors in the Monod
180 parameters ratio (Eq. (4)) and the half-life (step-7) estimates, related to the modeling
181 step, are in the $\sim 20\%$ level (fourfold the provoked error). Thus, globally, the calibration
182 step linked to the conventional approach becomes risky in terms of unreliable
183 estimations.

184 Table 2b results correspond to simulated errors in the analytical signal, again
185 affecting either to E1 or both enantiomers. In this case, the impact of constant (Ec) or
186 proportional (Ep) errors in the analytical signal (A) affect both strategies, but at different
187 degrees depending on the parameter.

188 A constant error (Ec) in the E1 signal equally affects the biodegradability (Eq.
189 (2) and (2a)) and the enantiomeric fraction estimates (Eq. (3) and (3a)). However,
190 interestingly, the lowest impact on EF is obtained using the alternative Eq. (3b). In all

191 cases, the *EF* errors are time-dependent, which creates, as before, the false conclusion
192 of a progressive enantioselective biodegradation process. On the other hand, the errors
193 corresponding to the Monod parameters ratio and the half-life estimates are lower for
194 the alternative model proposed in this work (Eq. 4a; errors at the 5 % level) than in the
195 conventional one (Eq. 4; errors at the 20 % level). This last fact is also observed in the
196 case of constant errors affecting both enantiomers.

197 In the case of a proportional error (*Ep*) over the signal values, the alternative Eq.
198 3b fully eliminates the errors in *EF* (still present using Eq. (3) and (3a), when E1 is
199 involved). In addition, the alternative Eq. (4a) avoids errors in the Monod parameters
200 ratio and the half-life estimates, which in contrast are present using the conventional
201 approach (error ~15 % level; Eq. (4) and step-7 in Table 1). It is then remarkable the
202 superiority of the alternative approach.

203 Combining the results in Tables 2a and 2b (8 simulated systematic errors), the
204 number of erroneous outputs over the biodegradability estimates decreases from 5 to 2
205 when using the alternative approach. Similarly, for the enantiomeric fraction this
206 number decreases from 3 to 2 (Eq. 3a) or 0 (Eq. 3b) and in the case of the Monod
207 parameters ratio and the half-life, it decreases from 8 (the maximum value) to 2. As can
208 be seen, the conventional calculations show in all cases higher frequency of errors than
209 the corresponding alternative ones. This evidences that globally, the alternative
210 approach is preferable (more accurate) to perform parameter estimations.

211

212 **Conclusions**

213 Systematic errors are ubiquitous in experiments, so they are present in any
214 (enantioselective or not) biodegradation process and/or in the further analytical

215 measurement step, including method calibration. The alternative approach evaluated in
216 this work is simple (i.e. it substitutes conventional variables by others mathematically
217 equivalent), but remarkably improves the global accuracy of the estimates. For instance,
218 the use of the novel Monod equation proposed in this work, just substituting the
219 concentration by biodegradability data (that could be estimated directly from the
220 analytical signals), drastically reduces or eliminates the impact of systematic errors on
221 rate constant and half-life time estimates (related to chemical persistence in the
222 environment).

223 From the results in this work, it can be concluded that the alternative approach:
224 (i) cancels all the impact of systematic errors due to calibration present in the
225 conventional approach; (ii) minimizes (mainly constant errors) or eliminates
226 (proportional errors, if Eq. 3b is selected) the effect of systematic errors during the
227 biodegradation/analytical processes related to the measured signal. It is clear to
228 conclude that the alternative approach is the best option to perform estimations that
229 would influence decisions on risk assessment. The results also suggest that probably,
230 many estimations performed in the past could be erroneous in some extent, considering
231 that the systematic errors are generally unknown.

232 Final inputs for calculations are usually the mean of several measurements (from
233 parallel batches). Such signals are affected by both systematic and random errors. This
234 work provides equations that reduce or eliminate the systematic part of the error but not
235 the random components, thus an uncertainty will always remain in this kind of
236 estimations.

237

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241

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279

Table 1a

Conventional approach to estimate environmentally relevant parameters

Step	Action (per enantiomer, Ei; i = 1 or 2)	Step	Action (per enantiomer, Ei; i = 1 or 2)
1	Calibrate the method and estimate the linear regression parameters (b_0, b_1)	5	Fit the $S_{Ei,t}$ data to the Monod model (integrated form; Robinson and Tiedje, 1983) to estimate the Monod parameters (μ_m and K_s) and their ratio, $r = \mu_m/K_s$: $t = \frac{1}{\mu_m} \left[C_1 \ln \frac{Y(S_0 - S_{Ei,t}) + X_0}{X_0} - C_2 \ln \frac{S_{Ei,t}}{S_0} \right] \quad (4)$ where: $C_1 = (K_s Y + S_0 Y + X_0) / (Y S_0 + X_0)$ $C_2 = (K_s Y) / (Y S_0 + X_0)$
2	Measure analytical signals (A) of samples at incubation times (t) and estimate their concentrations (S): $S_{Ei,t} = \frac{A_{Ei,t} - b_0}{b_1} \quad (1)$	6	Generate an S - t depletion curve (with short t -increments) from Eq. (4) and the corresponding BD - t curve using Eq. (2)
3	Estimate the biodegradability in percentage (BD): $BD_{Ei,t} = 100 \frac{S_{Ei,0} - S_{Ei,t}}{S_{Ei,0}} \quad (2)$	7	Interpolate $BD = 50\%$ into the BD - t curve to estimate the half-life time (HL)
4	Estimate the enantiomeric fraction (EF): $EF_t = \frac{S_{E1,t}}{S_{E1,t} + S_{E2,t}} \quad (3)$		

Acronyms: Ei, enantiomer i (i.e. E1 or E2) ; b_0 , intercept; b_1 , slope; A , analytical signal; t , incubation time; S , concentration; S_0 , initial concentration; BD , biodegradability; EF , enantiomeric fraction; μ_m , maximum specific growth rate; K_s , Monod constant; Y , yield coefficient (mass of biomass per mass of substrate); r , Monod parameters ratio (r is proportional to a first-order rate constant if $S_0 \ll K_s$); X_0 , initial biomass concentration; HL , half-life time.

Table 1b

Alternative approach to estimate environmentally relevant parameters.

Step	Action (per enantiomer, Ei; i = 1 or 2)	Step	Action (per enantiomer, Ei; i = 1 or 2)
3a	Estimate BD based on A data (Escuder-Gilabert et al., 2018a): $BD_{Ei,t} = 100 \frac{A_{Ei,0} - A_{Ei,t}}{A_{Ei,0}} \quad (2a)$	5a	Fit the $BD_{Ei,t}$ data to the modified Monod model to estimate the Monod parameters and r : $t = \frac{1}{\mu_m} \left[C_1 \ln \frac{Y \left(S_0 \frac{BD_{Ei,t}}{100} \right) + X_0}{X_0} - C_2 \ln \left(1 - \frac{BD_{Ei,t}}{100} \right) \right] \quad (4a)$ where: C_1 and C_2 are as in Eq. (4). Eq (4a) is a new proposed model derived from Eq. (4) and Eq. (2)
4a	Estimate the enantiomeric fraction (EF) by two equations (Escuder-Gilabert et al., 2018a): $EF_t = \frac{A_{E1,t}}{A_{E1,t} + A_{E2,t}} \quad (3a)$ $EF_t = \frac{100 - BD_{E1,t}}{200 - BD_{E1,t} - BD_{E2,t}} \quad (3b)$ Eq. (3b) is obtained from Eq. (2a) and (3a)	6a	Generate a BD - t curve (with short t -increments) from Eq. (4a)
		7a	As step-7 in Table 1a

Acronyms as in Table 1a

286 **Table 2a**

287 Impacts of systematic errors in the calibration coefficients (b_0 or b_1) at 5 % level on the environmentally
 288 relevant parameters. Initial pollutant concentration ($S_0 = 0.001$); compatible with environmental
 289 conditions. Accurate equations (providing null or negligible errors) are not included.

Involved enantiomer	Input parameter	Value (Provoked error)	Erroneous parameters and involved Eq./steps in Tables 1a and 1b	Resultant error (%) in the parameter estimate
E1	b_0	$5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ (5 % at the calibration centroid level)	<i>S</i> ; Eq. (1) <i>BD</i> ; Eq. (2) <i>EF</i> ; Eq. (3) <i>r</i> ; Eq. (4) <i>HL</i> ; step 7	[-5.0, -6.0, -7.1] [NaN, +5.3, +5.3] [-2.6, -3.1, -3.7] -25.6 -20.4
E1 and E2	b_0	$5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ (5 % at the calibration centroid level)	<i>S</i> ; Eq. (1) <i>BD</i> ; Eq. (2) <i>r</i> ; Eq. (4) <i>HL</i> ; step 7	[-5.0, -6.0, -7.1] [NaN, +5.3, +5.3] -25.6 -20.4
E1	b_1	1.05 (5 % at all the calibration levels)	<i>S</i> ; Eq. (1) <i>EF</i> ; Eq. (3) <i>r</i> ; Eq. (4) <i>HL</i> ; step 7	[-4.8, -4.8, -4.8] [-2.4, -2.4, -2.4] +18.4 -15.7
E1 and E2	b_1	1.05 (5 % at all the calibration levels)	<i>S</i> ; Eq. (1) <i>BD</i> ; Eq. (2) <i>r</i> ; Eq. (4) <i>HL</i> ; step 7	[-4.8, -4.8, -4.8] [-2.4, -2.4, -2.4] +18.4 -15.7

290 Acronyms: NaN, non-available number (zero as numerator); the rest of acronyms as in Table 1a.

291

292 **Table 2b**

293 Impacts of systematic errors in the analytical signals (A) at 5 % level on the environmentally relevant
 294 parameters. Initial pollutant concentration ($S_0 = 0.001$); compatible with environmental conditions.
 295 Accurate equations (providing null or negligible errors) are not included.

Involved enantiomer	Input parameter	Value (Provoked error)	Erroneous parameters and involved Eq./steps in Tables 1a and 1b	Resultant error (%) in the parameter estimate
E1	Ec (All signals)	$+5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ (5 % at $t = 0$)	A and S ; Eq. (1) BD ; Eq. (2) and (2a) EF ; Eq. (3) and (3a) EF ; Eq. (3b) r ; Eq. (4) r ; Eq. (4a) HL ; step 7 HL ; step 7a	[+5.0, +6.0, +7.1] [NaN, -4.8, -4.8] [+2.4, +2.9, +3.4] [0.0, +0.5, +1.0] -19.8 -5.5 +24.7 +5.6
E1 and E2	Ec (All signals)	$+5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ (5 % at $t = 0$)	A and S ; Eq. (1) BD ; Eq. (2) and (2a) r ; Eq. (4) r ; Eq. (4a) HL ; step 7 HL ; step 7a	[+5.0, +6.0, +7.1] [NaN, -4.8, -4.8] -19.8 -5.5 +24.7 +5.6
E1	Ep (All signals)	(+5 % in all signals)	A and S ; Eq. (1) EF ; Eq. (3) and (3a) r ; Eq. (4) HL ; step 7	[+5.0, +5.0, +5.0] [+2.4, +2.4, +2.4] -14.4 +16.8
E1 and E2	Ep (All signals)	(+5 % in all signals)	A and S ; Eq. (1) r ; Eq. (4) HL ; step 7	[+5.0, +5.0, +5.0] -14.4 +16.8

296 Acronyms: Ec , constant error; Ep , proportional error; the rest of acronyms as in Tables 1a and 2a.

297